

NONLINEAR DYNAMICS AND CHAOS OF BUCKLED SANDWICH BEAMS
WITH ISOTROPIC OR LAMINATED COMPOSITE FACINGS

Y. Y. Yu

Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering
New Jersey Institute of Technology
Newark, New Jersey 07021, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

A recent phenomenon that has been leading to much excitement in many disciplines deals with chaos. Early studies of nonlinear dynamics and chaos of structures were associated with buckled beams, and they were carried out on the basis of the classical beam theory in which the transverse shear deformation is neglected. In this paper equations of motion are derived and a dynamical model is developed for the analysis of nonlinear dynamics and chaos of buckled sandwich beams with isotropic or laminated composite facings. The effect of transverse shear deformation is included, as this has been determined to be essential in previous studies on dynamics and vibration of both sandwich and laminated composite structures.

A review of the variational equation of motion in nonlinear elasticity theory is given first. A recently introduced special form of the equation is then employed to derive the equations of motion of the sandwich beams. A simple dynamical model is created for buckled sandwich beams with hinged ends by adopting a single-mode approximation, through the use of which the equations of motion are reduced to a Duffing's equation. Based on this equation, preliminary numerical analysis of chaos on the personal computer has been carried out, and the effect of damping is demonstrated.

KEY WORDS: Sandwich Construction; Nonlinear; Dynamic Response; Vibration; Buckling.

1. INTRODUCTION

A recent phenomenon that has been leading to much excitement in many disciplines deals with chaos. As indicated in a recent survey by Holmes (1), there have been over 50 technical books and 5000 research papers published on the subject in the past 10 years. We single out the books by Holmes (2), Guckenheimer and Holmes (3), Thompson and Stewart (4), and Moon (5).

Early studies of chaos in structural dynamics were associated with buckled beams. Nonlinear vibrations of buckled beams were investigated by Eisley (6) and by Tseng and Dugunji (7). Although the name "chaos" was not even mentioned, the phenomenon was observed experimentally and confirmed numerically by the latter authors. More recently, chaos in beams buckled by nonlinear magnetic body forces were investigated by Moon (5). All these previous works on nonlinear dynamics and chaos of buckled beams were based on the classical beam theory in which the transverse shear deformation is assumed to be negligible.

In this paper equations of motion are derived and a dynamical model is developed for the analysis of nonlinear dynamics and chaos of buckled sandwich beams. In contrast to previous studies of buckled beams (5,6,7), the effect of transverse shear deformation will be included. The importance of this effect in the dynamic analysis of sandwiches was well established in our early study (8). Its importance for layered structures in general, including also laminated composites, was further noted in a recent survey (9). Two types of sandwiches are considered here. Both are symmetrically constructed and have an isotropic core. While one has facings that are also isotropic, the other has identical laminated composite facings.

Derivation of the equations of the buckled sandwich beams is based on a recently introduced special form of the variational equation of motion in nonlinear elasticity theory. To start with, a brief account of the variational equations is given in the next section.

2. VARIATIONAL EQUATIONS OF MOTION IN NONLINEAR ELASTICITY

In developing equations of beams, plates, and shells, we have found it convenient to make use of the variational equations of motion in nonlinear elasticity theory. According to Love (10), Kirchhoff was apparently the first to formulate the variational equation of motion from Hamilton's principle in linear elasticity. In nonlinear elasticity we presented in an early work (11) a generalized Hamilton's principle and the associated variational equation of motion and discussed a number of special cases. To save space we summarize the results for a few cases in

the form of ordinary variational equations rather than their much lengthier generalized versions. The latter can be written similarly without difficulty.

2.1 Classical Nonlinear Case This case is associated with the widely used Green's nonlinear strain tensor whose components are

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ki} u_{k,j} + \delta_{kj} u_{k,i} + u_{k,i} u_{k,j}) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}[\delta_{ki}(e_{kj} + \omega_{kj}) + \delta_{kj}(e_{ki} + \omega_{ki}) \\ &\quad + (e_{ki} + \omega_{ki})(e_{kj} + \omega_{kj})] \quad (i, j, k=1, 2, 3) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where u_i are the displacements, e_{ij} the linear strains, ω_{ij} the rotations, and δ_{ij} the Kronecker delta. The corresponding variational equation of motion is

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt \int_V \{[\sigma_{ij}(\delta e_{lj} + e_{lj} + \omega_{lj})]_{,i} + f_l - \rho \ddot{u}_l\} \delta u_l \, dV \\ - \int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt \int_{S_p} \{\sigma_{ij}(\delta e_{lj} + e_{lj} + \omega_{lj})v_i - p_i\} \delta u_l \, dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{ij} are components of Kirchhoff's stress tensor. Equations (1) and (2) correspond to each other exactly in the variational sense (11).

2.2 Simplified Nonlinear Case This is a simplification of the above case in which the rotations are much larger than the linear strains, although both are much smaller than unity. As Novozhilov (12) suggested for this case, Eqs. (1) and (2) would reduce to, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{ij} &= e_{ij} + \frac{1}{2}\omega_{ki}\omega_{kj} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ki}e_{kj} + \delta_{kj}e_{ki} + \omega_{ki}\omega_{kj}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt \int_V \{[\sigma_{ij}(\delta e_{lj} + \omega_{lj})]_{,i} + f_l - \rho \ddot{u}_l\} \delta u_l \, dV \\ - \int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt \int_{S_p} \{\sigma_{ij}(\delta e_{lj} + \omega_{lj})v_i - p_i\} \delta u_l \, dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Unfortunately, Eqs. (3) and (4) no longer correspond to each other variationally. Indeed, it can be shown that a form of ϵ_{ij} corresponding to Eq. (4) does not exist, and only an expression

for $\delta\epsilon_{ij}$ is obtainable (11). In spite of such deficiency and because of its practical importance, we (11,13) have proposed to accept Eq. (4) as if it were a true variational equation. In fact, a new name has been coined recently (14) by referring to Eq. (4) as a pseudo-variational equation of motion.

2.3 New Simplified Nonlinear Case In component form, the integrands in the volume and surface integrals in Eq. (4) each consists of three terms associated with δu_x , δu_y , and δu_z , respectively, which are the variations of the displacements. To apply Eq. (4) to beams, plates, and shells let u_z be chosen in the thickness direction. We then propose to linearize terms associated with δu_x and δu_y and to keep only terms associated with δu_z in the original nonlinear form. In component form, the variational equation of motion for this recently introduced new case is as follows:

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt \int_V \{ [\partial\sigma_{xx}/\partial x + \partial\sigma_{yx}/\partial y + \partial\sigma_{zx}/\partial z + f_x - \rho\ddot{u}_x] \delta u_x + [\partial\sigma_{xy}/\partial x + \partial\sigma_{yy}/\partial y + \partial\sigma_{zy}/\partial z + f_y - \rho\ddot{u}_y] \delta u_y + [\partial(\sigma_{xz} - \sigma_{xx}\omega_{zx} + \sigma_{xy}\omega_{yz})/\partial x + \partial(\sigma_{yz} - \sigma_{yx}\omega_{zx} + \sigma_{yy}\omega_{yz})/\partial y + \partial(\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{zx}\omega_{zx} + \sigma_{zy}\omega_{yz})/\partial z + f_z - \rho\ddot{u}_z] \delta u_z \} dV - \int_{t_0}^{t_1} dt \int_{S_p} \{ [\sigma_{xx}n_x + \sigma_{yx}n_y + \sigma_{zx}n_z - p_x] \delta u_x + [\sigma_{xy}n_x + \sigma_{yy}n_y + \sigma_{zy}n_z - p_y] \delta u_y + [(\sigma_{xz} - \sigma_{xx}\omega_{zx} + \sigma_{xy}\omega_{yz}) n_x + (\sigma_{yz} - \sigma_{yx}\omega_{zx} + \sigma_{yy}\omega_{yz}) n_y + (\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{zx}\omega_{zx} + \sigma_{zy}\omega_{yz}) n_z - p_z] \delta u_z \} dS = 0 \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is similar to (4) in that a corresponding ϵ_{ij} does not exist; it is therefore also a pseudo-variational equation of motion. In the process of preparing a book (14), we have found it not only convenient but also informative to be able to use Eq. (5) in the derivation of equations for large deflections of plates of the von Kármán type and shallow shells of the Marguerre type, whether the transverse shear effect is included or not. It will be used here again to derive equations of the sandwich beams.

2.3 Linear Case Needless to say, all of the above nonlinear cases can be reduced to a common linear form. Also, the linear strains and the linear variational equation of motion correspond to each other exactly in the variational sense.

3. EQUATIONS OF SANDWICH BEAMS

The symmetric sandwich beam under consideration has an axis in the x-direction and two ends at $x = 0, \ell$. The width of the beam in the y-direction can be taken as b . However, it will be convenient to consider a unit width so that the treatment may also be applicable to a sandwich plate in plane strain. The middle plane of the beam or plate is thus taken to be the xy-plane. In the z-direction the thicknesses of the lower facing, core, and upper facing extend from $-h$ to $-h_1$, $-h_1$ to h_1 , and h_1 to h , respectively. The thickness of the core is then $2h_1$, that of each facing $h_2 = h - h_1$, and that of the entire sandwich $2h$. While the two facings are made of the same materials, the core is generally made of a different material. Ordinarily the facings have a higher density and stiffness than the core. The lower facing, core, and upper facing are designated by the subscripts 1, 2, and 3, respectively. When there is no need to distinguish between the two facings, both are referred to by a single subscript 2.

3.1 Variational Equation of Motion For the sandwich beam we assume as before (15,16) a perfect bond between adjacent layers by taking the displacements in the form

$$\begin{aligned} u_1 &= u + z\psi, & u_2, u_3 &= u \mp h_1\psi \\ v_i &= 0, & w_i &= w \quad (i=1,2,3) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

in which continuity at the interfaces between layers is assured and the beam-displacements u , w , and ψ are functions of x and t . We further take the rotations in the form

$$\omega_{yzi} = 0, \quad \omega_{zxi} = -\partial w / \partial x \quad (i=1,2,3) \quad (7)$$

Equations (6) and (7) are substituted into Eq. (5), in which the body forces are neglected. Integration in Eq. (5) is then carried out with respect to z over the thickness of each of the layers. After combining the results for all layers by enforcing also the continuity of tractions at the interfaces, the final result for the sandwich beam is found to be

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \int_0^{\ell} \{ [\partial(N_{x1} + N_{x2} + N_{x3}) / \partial x - 2(\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2) \ddot{u}] \delta u \\ & + [\partial(Q_{x1} + (N_{x1} + N_{x2} + N_{x3}) \partial w / \partial x \\ & + p_z - 2(\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2) \ddot{w})] \delta w \\ & + [\partial(M_{x1} + h_1(N_{x3} - N_{x2})) / \partial x - Q_{x1} - \frac{1}{2} \rho_1 h_1^3 \ddot{\psi}] \delta \psi \} dx dt \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \{ [N_{x1} + N_{x2} + N_{x3} - P_x^{(0)}] \delta u \\
& \quad + [Q_{x1} + (N_{x1} + N_{x2} + N_{x3}) \partial w / \partial x - p_z^{(0)}] \delta w \\
& \quad + [M_{x1} + h_1(N_{x3} - N_{x2}) - P_x^{(1)}] \delta \psi \} \Big|_{x=0}^{x=\ell} dt = 0 \quad (8)
\end{aligned}$$

where the lateral load p_z includes tractions at both top and bottom of the sandwich in the z -direction. In addition, the beam-stresses and the integrated tractions at the ends of the beam are defined by, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned}
(N_{xi}, Q_{x1}, M_{x1}) &= \int (\sigma_{xxi}, \sigma_{xz1}, \sigma_{xx1}z) dz \\
(p_x^{(0)}, p_z^{(0)}, p_x^{(1)}) &= \int (p_x, p_z, p_x z) dz \quad (9)
\end{aligned}$$

N_x , Q_x , and M_x are the usual axial membrane force, shearing force, and bending moment, respectively. The superscripts (0) and (1) refer to physical quantities of the zeroth and first orders, respectively.

According to the calculus of variations, three stress equations of motion valid for the length of the beam between $x = 0$ and $x = \ell$ can be written from the first integral in Eq. (8) by setting equal to zero the coefficients of δu , δw , and $\delta \psi$. Similarly, three traction boundary conditions at the ends $x = 0, \ell$ can be written from the second integral. Alternatively, displacement boundary conditions can be prescribed, by simply specifying u , w , and ψ at $x = 0, \ell$.

3.2 Stress Equations of Motion and Boundary Conditions The core of the sandwich is usually so much weaker than the facings that we take

$$N_{x1} = M_{x1} = 0$$

The stress equations of motion derived from Eq. (8) are then

$$\begin{aligned}
& (N_{x2} + N_{x3})' - 2(\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2) \ddot{u} = 0 \\
& [Q_{x1} + (N_{x2} + N_{x3})w']' + p_z - 2(\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2) \ddot{w} = 0 \quad (0 \leq x \leq \ell) \quad (10) \\
& [h_1(N_{x3} - N_{x2})]' - Q_{x1} - \frac{3}{2}\rho_1 h_1^3 \ddot{\psi} = 0
\end{aligned}$$

and the boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{x2} + N_{x3} &= p_x^{(0)} \quad \text{or} \quad u = \text{prescribed} \\
Q_{x1} + (N_{x2} + N_{x3})w' &= p_z^{(0)} \quad \text{or} \quad w = \text{prescribed} \\
h_1(N_{x3} - N_{x2}) &= p_x^{(1)} \quad \text{or} \quad \psi = \text{prescribed} \quad (11)
\end{aligned}$$

where a prime is now used to denote differentiation with respect to x . Equations (10) and (11) are valid for a sandwich with either isotropic or laminated composite facings. It is only the stress-strain relations that are different between the two types of facings. In these equations the sum $(N_{x2} + N_{x2}')$ is the resultant axial force, its component $(N_{x2} + N_{x3}) \partial w / \partial x$ combined with Q_{x1} gives the total shearing force, and $h_1(N_{x2} - N_{x3})$ serves as the bending moment.

3.3 Stress-Strain-Displacement Relations To express the stress equations of motion and traction boundary conditions in terms of displacements, we need relations between the beam-stresses and beam-displacements. Let us consider first the axial forces N_{x2} and N_{x3} in isotropic facings.

3.3.1 Axial Forces in Isotropic Facings At the outset we note again that the stresses in Eqs. (2), (4), and (5) are components of Kirchhoff's stress tensor. In nonlinear elasticity theory these stress components are known to be associated with the components of Green's nonlinear strain tensor through the strain-energy function in a similar manner as linear stresses and strains are related to each other in linear elasticity (14). Thus, for an isotropic elastic layer in a state of plane stress, the nonlinear stress-strain relations can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{xx_i} &= E_2(\epsilon_{xx_i} + \epsilon_{yy_i}) / (1 - \nu_2^2) \\ \sigma_{yy_i} &= E_2(\epsilon_{yy_i} + \epsilon_{xx_i}) / (1 - \nu_2^2) \quad (i=2,3) \\ \sigma_{xy_i} &= 2G_2\epsilon_{xy_i}\end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where ϵ_{xx_i} and ϵ_{yy_i} are the nonlinear normal strains; E_2 , ν_2 , and G_2 are the usual Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, and shear modulus, respectively; and a factor of 2 has been attached to ϵ_{xy_i} because it is the nonlinear tensorial, not engineering, shearing strain. In the case of plane strain in which only ϵ_{xx_i} is present, the first of these relations reduces to

$$\sigma_{xx_i} = E_2\epsilon_{xx_i} / (1 - \nu_2^2) \quad (i=2,3) \quad (13)$$

This is the only stress needed for deriving N_{x2} and N_{x3} . Corresponding to ϵ_{xx_i} the stress σ_{yy_i} will also be present, but σ_{xy_i} will not. For application to a beam Eq. (13) is simply replaced by

$$\sigma_{xx_i} = E_2\epsilon_{xx_i} \quad (i=2,3) \quad (14)$$

For the simplified cases in nonlinear elasticity discussed in Section 2, the nonlinear strain component ϵ_{xx_i} has the form

$$\epsilon_{xx_i} = u_1' + \frac{1}{2}\omega_{xx_i}^2 \quad (15)$$

Equations (12) through (15) are relations from nonlinear elasticity theory. For the membrane facings we substitute u_2, u_3 from Eqs. (6) and $\omega_{xx2}, \omega_{xx3}$ from Eqs. (7) into Eqs. (15), (13), and (9), in that order. The final results are, for the facings in plane strain,

$$\begin{aligned} (N_{x2}, N_{x3}) &= E_2 h_2 (\epsilon_{xx2}^{(0)}, \epsilon_{xx3}^{(0)}) / (1 - v_2^2) \\ &= E_2 h_2 [u' + h_1 \psi' + \frac{1}{2}(w')^2] / (1 - v_2^2) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\epsilon_{xx2}^{(0)}, \epsilon_{xx3}^{(0)}$ are nonlinear normal strains of zeroth order, uniform over the facing thickness. Similar results for a beam are obtained by simply replacing $(1 - v_2^2)$ by 1, but N_{x2}, N_{x3} are still forces per unit length in the direction of the beam width. To obtain the total axial force in a beam these must be further multiplied by the width of the beam.

3.3.2 Axial Forces in Laminated Composite Facings Let us consider first a single ply in unidirectional composites in a state of plane stress, for which the stress-strain relations are (17,18)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{66} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{16} \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & Q_{26} \\ Q_{61} & Q_{62} & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ 2\epsilon_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

where a factor of 2 is again attached to the nonlinear tensorial shearing strain ϵ_{66} , and Q_{ij} are the off-axis stiffnesses. For a symmetric multidirectional laminate consisting of an arbitrary number of plies, integration of Eqs. (17) over the thickness of the laminate yields

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{61} & A_{62} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx}^{(0)} \\ \epsilon_{yy}^{(0)} \\ 2\epsilon_{xy}^{(0)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where A_{ij} are the extensional (in-plane) stiffnesses of the laminate. If the total number of plies in the laminate is n and the k -th ply extends from $z = h^{(k-1)}$ to $z = h^{(k)}$, the extensional stiffness of the laminate is given by

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n Q_{ij}^{(k)} (h^{(k)} - h^{(k-1)}) \quad (19)$$

where $Q_{ij}^{(k)}$ is the off-axis stiffness of the k -th ply. It is noted that the strains on the right-hand side of Eqs. (18) are constant in all plies.

To apply Eqs. (18) to the facings of the sandwich, we insert as before a subscript $i = 2$ or 3 to all quantities. Since $\epsilon_{xxi}^{(0)}$ is

the only strain that is not zero in these equations, we find

$$(N_{x2}, N_{x3}) = (A_{11})_2 (\epsilon_{xx2}^{(0)}, \epsilon_{xx3}^{(0)}) \quad (20)$$

There is no need to introduce $(A_{11})_3$ since it is the same as $(A_{11})_2$. Comparing Eqs. (20) with (16), we see that $(A_{11})_2$ has taken the place of $E_2 h_2 / (1 - \nu_2^2)$. Equations (16) and (20) may therefore be written in a combined form, as follows:

$$(N_{x2}, N_{x3}) = K_2 (\epsilon_{xx2}^{(0)}, \epsilon_{xx3}^{(0)}) = K_2 [u' \mp h_1 \psi' + \frac{1}{2}(w')^2] \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} K_2 &= E_2 h_2 / (1 - \nu_2^2) \quad \text{for isotropic facings} \\ &= (A_{11})_2 \quad \text{for laminated composite facings} \end{aligned}$$

According to Eqs. (18), a non-zero $\epsilon_{xxi}^{(0)}$ by itself will induce an N_{yi} as well as N_{xi} due to Poisson's effect just as in the case of isotropic facings. In addition, however, an N_{xyi} will also be induced unless A_{61} vanishes; such coupling between in-plane normal and shearing forces has no counterpart in the isotropic case.

3.3.3 Shearing Force in Isotropic Core This is simply given by

$$Q_{x1} = 2G_1 h_1 (\psi + w') \quad (22)$$

where no shear correction factor is used. Alternatively, it may be said that a shear correction factor has been taken equal to 1 according to our early study (19) of simple thickness-shear modes of vibration in an infinite sandwich plate.

3.4 Displacement Equations of Motion To concentrate on the lateral motion of a sandwich beam we keep only the inertia term in the lateral direction in the second of Eqs. (10) and drop the inertia terms in the other two of these equations. According to the reduced form of the first of Eqs. (10) the resultant axial force $(N_{x2} + N_{x3})$ is then independent of x and thus uniform throughout the entire length of the beam. The sum of the two forces is found from Eqs. (21) to be

$$N_{x2} + N_{x3} = K_2 (\epsilon_{xx2}^{(0)} + \epsilon_{xx3}^{(0)}) = 2K_2 [u' + \frac{1}{2}(w')^2]$$

Simple integration of this result over the length of the beam further yields

$$N_{x2} + N_{x3} = K_2 (2/\ell) [u_0 + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\ell (w')^2 dx] \quad (23)$$

where u_0 is the relative axial displacement between the two ends

of the beam. By means of Eqs. (21) through (23), the second and third of Eqs. (10) become

$$2K_2h_1^2 \psi'''' + K_2(2/\ell)[u_0 + \int_0^\ell (w')^2 dx] w'' + P_z = 2(\rho_1h_1 + \rho_2h_2) \ddot{w} \quad (24)$$

$$2G_1h_1 (\psi + w') = 2K_2h_1^2 \psi'' \quad (25)$$

which are the displacement equations of motion.

4. BUCKLED SANDWICH BEAMS WITH HINGED ENDS

For sandwich beams with hinged ends a simple dynamical model may be constructed by adopting a single-mode approximation. The equations of motion of sandwich beams are then reduced to a Duffing's equation.

4.1 Single-Mode Formulation For a hinged sandwich beam we take

$$w = W \tau(t) \sin(\pi x/\ell), \quad \psi = \Psi \tau(t) \cos(\pi x/\ell)$$

Equation (25) then gives

$$\Psi = - \frac{1}{1 + (K_2/G_1h_1)(\pi^2h_1^2/\ell^2)} \frac{\pi W}{\ell} = -\beta \frac{\pi W}{\ell} \quad (26)$$

By making use of this result and further taking the lateral load in the form

$$P_z = P_z \sin(\pi x/\ell) \cos(\omega t)$$

ω being the forcing frequency, Eq. (24) becomes

$$2(\rho_1h_1 + \rho_2h_2)W\ddot{\tau} + 2K_2(\beta\pi^4h_1^2/\ell^4 + \pi^2u_0/\ell^3)W\tau + \frac{1}{2}K_2\pi^4W^3\tau^3/\ell^4 = P_z \cos(\omega t) \quad (27)$$

To incorporate buckling explicitly into the formulation, we solve Eq. (27) for the linear natural frequency by ignoring the nonlinear term, the result being

$$\omega_1^2 = [K_2/(\rho_1h_1 + \rho_2h_2)](\beta\pi^4h_1^2/\ell^4 + \pi^2u_0/\ell^3)$$

At inception of buckling, ω_1 becomes zero. The value of u_0 derived for this situation will be denoted by u_{cr} , given by

$$u_{cr}/\ell = -\beta(\pi h_1/\ell)^2$$

We now introduce the ratio

$$r = - u_0/u_{cr}$$

which may also be interpreted as the ratio of the applied axial load to the critical buckling load. In terms of r , Eq. (27) takes the final form

$$2(\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2)W\ddot{t} + 2K_2 h_1^2 (\pi^4/\ell^4)\beta(1-r)W\tau + (\pi^4/2\ell^4)K_2 W^3 \tau^3 = P_2 \sin(\omega t) \quad (28)$$

It is interesting to note that, for incipient buckling for which $r = 1$, the second term drops out, and the parameter β also disappears from the equation. This particular situation is then no longer dependent upon the transverse shear effect, since this effect is imbedded in the parameter β only.

4.2 Dynamics and Chaos Similar to the equations of motion of buckled classical beams, Eq. (28) for sandwich beams have the form of a Duffing's equation. Equations of similar form have also appeared in nonlinear vibration analysis of plates and shells, of both homogeneous and layered types (16,20,21). Such applications in structural dynamics, together with many others in various fields, have made Duffing's equation one of the most studied in nonlinear dynamics, and more recently in chaos. A very comprehensive numerical study has been carried out by Ueda (22) for chaos exhibited by the following reduced form of Duffing's equation:

$$\ddot{x} + k\dot{x} + x^3 = B \cos t \quad (29)$$

which does not have a term linear in x . As further shown by Thompson and Stewart (4), chaos are associated with Duffing's equation in the following more general form:

$$\ddot{x} + k\dot{x} + ax + x^3 = B \cos t \quad (30)$$

where a linear term ax is present and the coefficient a can be positive or negative or zero.

Except for a missing viscous damping term, Eq. (28) is similar to Eq. (30). In fact, Eq. (28) can be cast in the exact form of Eq. (30) by adding such a damping term and by writing

$$W\tau = cx$$

with

$$c = 2h_1/\omega_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_0^2 = K_2 h_1^2 \pi^4/\ell^4 (\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2)$$

This makes the coefficients of the inertia and cubic terms each

equal to one and the coefficients a and B equal to

$$a = \omega_0^2 \beta (1 - r), \quad B = P_z \omega_0 / 4h_1 (\rho_1 h_1 + \rho_2 h_2)$$

Duffing's equation in the form of Eq. (30) is one of the equations that can be treated by the computer software called Phaser, developed by Kocak (23) for numerical experimentation of dynamical systems. By means of Phaser, for instance, results on chaos obtained by Ueda from Eq. (29) and by Thompson and Stewart from Eq. (30) can be reproduced. It is therefore also applicable to Eq. (28) for the numerical analysis of nonlinear dynamics and chaos of sandwich beams.

Some preliminary numerical results have been obtained to demonstrate the effect of damping on chaos. Presented in Fig. 1 are the plots of the time history, phase portrait, and Poincaré map for a conservative system with $k = 0$ (zero damping), $a = 0$, $B = 7.5$, and zero initial conditions. In Fig. 2 similar plots are presented for a dissipative system with $k = 0.05$ (non-zero damping) and everything else being the same. In each figure the time history and phase portrait are for a small beginning part of the motion. Because of the difference in damping, details of the time histories of the two systems also differ. However, the general outlook of the phase portraits of the two systems is similar, and both indicate the occurrence of chaos. The Poincaré maps are for the entire time period for which calculation has been made and are clearly very different for the two systems. Above all, the overall size of the map in Fig. 2 is smaller than that in Fig. 1 because of damping. More importantly, while both maps again show the presence of chaos, the one in Fig. 1 for the conservative system shows complete chaos. In contrast, the map in Fig. 2 shows the typical folding action that takes place in a dissipative system. The phase portrait and Poincaré map for the dissipative system were given by Ueda (21) previously, and his results are confirmed here. However, he did not mention any system with zero damping.

Chaos in conservative systems have been of interest to researchers in physics for some time. On the other hand, recent efforts of many other researchers tend to deal almost exclusively with chaos in dissipative systems. For instance, the simple results for zero damping in Fig. 1 do not seem to have been reported before. The contrast in chaotic behaviors between conservative and dissipative systems as shown here appears to be interesting.

Now that a nonlinear dynamical model has been created for sandwich beams, numerical experimentation based on the model can next be carried out. It will also be important to confirm the theoretical and numerical results by laboratory experiments.

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Dr. Y.Y. Yu has been Professor of Mechanical Engineering since 1981 and Dean of Engineering until 1985 at NJIT. He is a Life Fellow of ASME, an Associate Fellow of AIAA, and a member of ASC and other societies. He has published widely and is preparing a book on the dynamics and vibration of plates and shells.

Fig. 1 A conservative system: $k = 0$, $a = 0$, $B = 7.5$, zero initial conditions. Top: time history for $t = 0$ to 250. Middle: phase portrait for $t = 0$ to 250. Bottom: Poincaré map for $t = 0$ to 20000.

Fig. 2 A dissipative system: $k = 0.05$,
 $a = 0$, $B = 7.5$, zero initial conditions.
 Top: time history for $t = 0$ to 250.
 Middle: phase portrait for $t = 0$ to 250.
 Bottom: Poincaré map for $t = 0$ to 20000.

